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Neuroendocrinology

Composite-drugs for the treatment of H63D Syndrome Type-3 (Oshtoran Syndrome)

Abstract

Oshtoran Syndrome, also known as H63D Syndrome Type-3, is a rare systemic medical condition characterized by a cascading progression of various disease processes. This leads to a dangerously broad variety of autonomic dysfunctions and consequential structural organ damages. Globally, there is not a single approved pharmaceutical treatment for this severe and potentially life-threatening syndrome. In this report, we introduce composite medications that have proven to be effective in individual treatment attempts. Please observe the warnings and the disclaimer attentively, as these are highly potent medications associated with a significant risk of severe adverse side effects.

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Oshtoran Syndrome

Among all rare diseases Oshtoran Syndrome is one of the most insidious, primarily rooted in PANS syndrome, rheumatic fever, or similar conditions experienced during early life stages. These initial conditions may instigate clinical features of a secondary H63D syndrome in individuals bearing a homozygous H63D mutation which must not be confused with hemochromatosis. After a while H63D syndrome's NTBI accumulation effects lead to extensive mitochondrial dysfunction and autonomic dysregulation across multiple organ systems. The pathology of Oshtoran Syndrome entails autonomic dysfunction within the central nervous system (CNS), autonomic nervous system (ANS), and the innate immune system, especially pronounced in advanced disease stages. Patients may exhibit a wide spectrum of neurologic, endocrinological, and immunologic disorders. Notable symptoms include neuropsychiatric manifestations, motor impairments akin to non-motor Parkinson's symptoms, cognitive impairment, atypical motor and perceptual disturbances, tic disorders, and the slow degeneration of the substantia nigra. Diagnostically, elevated levels of certain blood and urine parameters like eosinophils, basophils, kynurenine, kynurenine acid, TRY/KYN ratio, (nor-)epinephrine, and other catecholamines as well as cortisol are observed. Imaging might reveal fatty changes in the liver along with nodular hyperplasia (FNH). The syndrome was initially studied in Iran and traces back to an Iranian patient and her descendants from the Zagros Mountains. It garnered renewed attention in 2017 when the Marvel entertainment company used Oshtoran Syndrome excessively as a fate determining illness in its "Spider-Man" PS4 entertainment products. In the academic realm Oshtoran Syndrome experienced quite some limelight in

2022/2023 through the efforts of a research team led by H63D pioneer researcher Jacob Adams. The very complex pathogenesis of Oshtoran Syndrome encompasses a blend of genetic disorders, mitochondrial dysfunction, and disorders of kynurenine metabolism. Currently, Oshtoran Syndrome remains incurable, albeit to some extent treatable. Treatment primarily revolves around anti-inflammatory therapies, calming down the body's alarm systems (catecholamines) and address symptoms in order to improve the quality of life of those affected. An interdisciplinary approach is deemed critical, balancing symptom management with long-term pharmaceutical strategies to enhance patient outcomes.

Details

The underlying pathophysiology of Oshtoran Syndrome is complex and not yet fully understood. However, it is known to emerge from dysfunctional immune system processes, primarily rooted in PANS syndrome, rheumatic fever, or similar conditions experienced during early life stages. These initial conditions may instigate clinical features of a secondary H63D syndrome in individuals bearing a homozygous H63D mutation. This leads to extensive mitochondrial dysfunction due to damages caused by NTBI and autonomic dysregulation across multiple organ systems. The pathology entails autonomic dysfunction within the CNS, ANS, and the innate immune system, especially pronounced in advanced disease stages. Patients with Oshtoran Syndrome may exhibit a very wide range of symptoms, including neuropsychiatric manifestations, non-motor impairments akin to Parkinson's symptoms, cognitive impairment, idiosyncratic motor and perceptual disturbances, tic disorders, and degeneration of the substantia nigra. Elevated levels of certain blood and urine parameters like eosinophils, basophils, kynurenine, kynurenine acid and TRY/KYN ratio, bilirubin, especially important high levels of epinephrine, norepinephrine, and catecholamines are observed. Imaging might reveal fatty changes in the liver along with nodular hyperplasia (FNH).

Diagnostic Challenges

Early diagnosis of the syndrome is, as utmost important as it is, notably challenging due to its

complex and multifaceted symptomatology. Indicators such as unexplained liver disease, neurological and/or neuropsychiatric symptoms, and a shift in the tryptophan/kynurenine ratio could herald the presence of this rare syndrome, especially if they manifest following a sudden onset of disease during childhood or adolescence. Upon detection of these alarm signs, a comprehensive diagnostic workup is initiated, necessitating an interdisciplinary approach.

Treatment Modalities

Currently, Oshtoran Syndrome remains incurable, albeit treatable. Treatment primarily revolves around anti-inflammatory and symptomatic pharmacological therapies. An interdisciplinary approach is critical, balancing symptom management with long-term therapeutic strategies to enhance patient outcomes. Future research aims to unravel the underlying mechanisms of Oshtoran Syndrome to devise effective therapeutic interventions, thereby ameliorating the quality and expectancy of life for the afflicted individuals. Until now, at least two composite medications of older compounds (designed by using already fully licensed medical drugs) have been made available for patients suffering from Oshtoran Syndrome. One is Amitradicain, developed by Dr. Ali Asgari on request and with the support of the International H63D Syndrome Research Consortium, Amitradicain is a patent-free medication blended together to alleviate the chaotic signal transmission from the nervous system to the organs via innervation. In this regards the medication has shown robust efficacy in a series of individual treatment trials. It is not produced by the pharmaceutical industry but is prepared directly in pharmacies, following the specialized doctor's formula. Due to its side effect profile, treatment should commence in a hospital setting for patients with heart conditions, obesity, respiratory issues, or other severe symptoms. Despite its high risk profile, Amitradicain holds high hopes for improving the quality of life for those afflicted with Oshtoran Syndrome. Amitradil, and Travastil on the other hand, are related and entirely patent-free compost-pharmaceuticals to Amitradicain without procain for those patients whose heart and blood sugar regulation has already become affected by the consequences of Oshtoran Syndrome.

Composite- Pharmaceuticals

In the pharmaceutical industry, worldwide, the development of new, expensive drugs for orphan diseases is understandably of limited interest, leaving both patients and physicians often empty-handed, resorting to the off-label use of already approved drugs while closely monitoring their effects on a case-by-case basis. However, the scenario for Oshtoran Syndrome is somewhat distinct, as to our knowledge, for the first time, a series of composite drugs are being employed. Composite pharmaceuticals are mixtures of injection solutions from different drugs, combined in a clearly defined ratio utilizing physical forces to form a medication. The effects of this medication significantly differ from those of simultaneous but separate intake of the individual components. These composite drugs are considered individual treatment attempts under the responsibility of the treating physician.

Management, Limitations, and Disclaimer

The composite pharmaceuticals mentioned hereafter represent rationales aiming to protect the most common ANS derangements and subsequently the organs from cascading effects through innervation. For easier recall, we have named these compositions, also to alleviate patients' unnecessary fears of polypharmacy, potentially triggering a nocebo effect. The type and quantities of components as well as the frequency of administration are to be determined and monitored by the respective treating physician. Unless otherwise indicated, injection solutions intended for deep intramuscular administration are implied.

IV administration should be avoided, as should subcutaneous injection as well as s.c. infusion.

Manufacturing is usually carried out by pharmacies or small pharmaceutical companies in most countries, which also produce small quantities. The liability for prescription and application of the composite pharmaceuticals presented hereafter, which have considerable risks and side effects, lies with the treating physician. Their use is always an individual

therapy attempt when standard drugs are no longer an option. The authors of this report disclaim any liability and refer to the sole responsibility of the practitioner.

Amitradicain

A standard yet potent medication for Oshtoran Syndrome, Amitradicain, is generally well-tolerated in severe disease states. It comprises:

Alprazolam	2 mg
Midazolam	5mg
Tramadol	100mg
Dimetindene Maleate	4mg
Procaine	40mg

The dosages indicate an average mixing ratio. The prescribing physician should adjust the quantities as per individual patient tolerability and safety.

In the Amitradicain composition, Alprazolam plays a crucial off-label role as it is the only well-tolerated drug that reduces adrenaline synthesis in the renal medulla (Breier et al., 1992). A significant synergy was observed between Dimetindene Maleate, Midazolam, and Tramadol, which also enhances the effects of Procaine on the nervous system.

Procaine has a central balancing and activating effect on the parasympathetic system. However, caution is required in patients with impaired cardiac health, especially those with conduction abnormalities. Patients with diabetes mellitus should also be handled with extra caution.

Amitradil

For existing cardiac symptoms and mitochondrial pathology, Amitradil, substituting Procaine, could be a viable option:

Alprazolam	2 mg
Midazolam	5 mg
Tramadol	75 mg
Clemastine	4 mg
Dimetindene Maleate	4 mg
Bromelain 500 FIP	500 FIP units p.o.

Travalin

When the skin is significantly affected, Travalin often shows satisfactory effects:

Diazepam 15 mg i.m.
(not to be mixed with the other compounds)

Tramadol 200 mg
Clemastine 4 mg
Dimetindene Maleate 4 mg
Procaine 30 mg
Prednisolone 10 mg

Upon therapy response, the corticosteroid dose should be gradually reduced to the lowest effective dose. The use of biologics is discouraged due to their lack of broad efficacy.

Pritacosin

In the occurrence of new cardiac symptoms, without a cardiologist finding another cause (emergency treatment and/or exclusion diagnosis), it is worth attempting the following composition for 5 days in confirmed Oshtoran Syndrome cases. The corticosteroid dose should be reduced to the lowest effective dose over time upon therapy response.

Prednisolone 250 mg
Candesartan 4 mg
Doxazosin 8 mg
Dimetindene Maleate 20 mg
Tramadol 100 mg
N-Acetylcysteine 300 mg
Bromelain 1000 FIP unit p.o.

Ditranidol

When cognitive impairments, neurological issues and neuropsychiatric symptoms are significantly pronounced, the following composite medication has often proven highly effective in a portion of patients during individual treatment trials:

Diphenhydramine 50 mg
Prednisolone 5 mg
Clonazepam 2 mg p.o.
Aspirin 300 mg
Tramadol 125 mg
Dimetinden 4 mg
Dextromethorphan 20 mg

N-Acetylcysteine 600 mg
Propranolol 40 mg

Caution: Patients with Oshtoran Syndrome often exhibit paradoxical reactions to SSRIs, SNRIs, and other traditional psychotropic drugs.

Atraminolam

In addition to amitradicaine, the formulation described below has been used for the longest time in individual therapeutic trials in patients. According to the available internal documents, it helps mainly patients with already manifested organ impairment (especially substantia nigra, heart, liver) and those who have significant non-motor symptoms characteristically very similar to that in Parkinson's disease.

Alprazolam 2 mg
Propranolol 40 mg
N-Acetylcysteine 600 mg
Clonazepam 2 mg
Tramadol 100 mg
Prednisolon 40 mg
Dimetindene Maleate 4 mg
RRR-a-Tocopherol 800 I.U.

Diamitralon

This composition, entailing a regimen of tablets coupled with two injections, is not particularly favored by patients due to its complexity. However, it was rated the highest in terms of efficacy, favorable clinical course for the patients, and improvement of general condition, according to a survey conducted among prescribing specialists for rare diseases.

Alprazolam 2 mg p.o.
As a tablet 20 minutes before the injection of all other compounds.

or

Midazolam 5 mg i.m.
Tramadol 100 mg i.m.
Prednisolon 10 mg i.m.
Dimetindene Maleate 4 mg i.m.
Clemastin 2 mg i.m.

and

Diazepam 10 mg i.m.
(DZM always to be administered in a separate syringe!)

and

Propranolol 40 mg p.o.
Doxazosin 4 mg p.o.

Warning and Disclaimer

The prescription and administration of the composite pharmaceuticals delineated herein, bearing significant risks and potential adverse reactions, are solely within the purview and responsibility of the treating physician. The utilization of these composite pharmaceuticals is consistently regarded as an individualized therapeutic endeavor when conventional pharmaceutical alternatives are deemed ineffective or inappropriate. The authors of this document, along with their affiliated institutions, expressly disclaim any and all liability, be it direct, indirect, consequential, special, exemplary, or other damages arising from or in connection with the prescription, administration, or use of the composite pharmaceuticals discussed herein. The treating physician bears the unequivocal responsibility for discerning the suitability, potential risks, and benefits of these composite pharmaceuticals for each patient, and for navigating and adhering to the applicable regulatory and professional standards governing such therapeutic endeavors. This document does not constitute medical advice, endorsement, or recommendation for the use of any pharmaceuticals, and the authors emphatically reiterate the exclusive liability of the treating physician in the prescription and administration of the composite pharmaceuticals. The contents of this document are for informational purposes only and are not a substitute for professional medical advice, diagnosis, or treatment.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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References

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